

GLAZBENA PEDAGOGIJA U SVJETLU SADAŠNJIH I BUDUĆIH PROMJENA 9

*Formalni, neformalni i informalni glazbeni
odgoj i obrazovanje: istraživanje i praksa*

MUSIC PEDAGOGY IN THE CONTEXT OF PRESENT AND FUTURE CHANGES 9

*Formal, Non-Formal, and Informal Music
Education: Research and Practice*

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THE IMPACT OF DANCE EDUCATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Dance education at least, in North Macedonia, has been neglected within the elementary school curriculum, except two elective subjects. While this approach is prevalent in North Macedonia, many developed countries advocate for the segmentation of artistic subjects and the inclusion of dance as an independent subject of education at various levels, often supported by multi-year programs. The question arises: Should dance be established as an independent subject in school curriculums, and what advantages would such a pedagogical approach offer? The answer is undoubtedly affirmative. Dance has been recognized for its significant positive impact on student development. The benefits are manifold. To obtain a more comprehensive understanding, I have categorized the positive impacts of this educational approach into several distinct groups. Firstly, dance training methods have been shown to significantly enhance students' memory processes. Secondly, these methods contribute to the development of coordination and motor skills. Thirdly, the substantial effect of dance serves as a potent stimulus for creative development. Given the prevalence of anxiety, aggression, and negative emotions in contemporary society, research has demonstrated the beneficial psychological effects of dance. The discussion and analysis of the paper will emphasize the physical, mental and creative development of children connected with dancing practices. To substantiate these claims, I will present relevant scientific research conducted in recent years, which has yielded specific, quantifiable results.

Keywords: dance, education, effects, elementary school, students

General Starting Points

It is a common belief that dancing and music serve primarily as sources of enjoyment and do not play a significant role in developmental processes, including mental, creative, and social aspects. Nevertheless, research challenges these stereotypical views. Dancing encompasses not only improvisation but also adheres to established rules of training, systematic approaches, and methodologies of study. What is dance education? What assignments does it define, what are the effects, the contributions and the projections of its application? Along with dance development, these questions are constantly being updated and discussed. We follow responses that most frequently correspond to priorities, the established tasks, the education format, and still despite various approaches we come across mutual fundamental values. "In order to elevate dance to its perfection, a school is needed that would teach dancers to be somewhere between their body and spiritual being, by simultaneously perfecting both components" (Noverre, 1965, p. 200), wrote Jean-Georges Noverre in 1760 in his unique, yet exceptional

book *Letters on Dancing and Ballets*. The choreographer, pioneer of modern dance, Isadora Duncan interpreted this type of education from a different angle in a strong, feminist manner, and she noted: "The dancing school of future is to develop and to show the ideal form of woman. It will be, as it were, a museum of the living beauty of the period (...) More than this, dancing like any art of any time should reflect the highest point of mankind has reached in this special period" (Duncan, 1992, p. 128). In an almost identical direction are the contemplations of one of the most significant figures in the Macedonian dance education, the Russian pedagogue Yuri Myachin, who focuses on a specific form of dance education. He writes: "The school of classical ballet – a system of physical and mental education, guides you to perfect mastery of dance technique, to subjugate that technique to the ballet art tasks. The appropriate, directed, elaborated course of dance training, educates and acts upon the human organism as a whole" (Myachin, 2003, p. 133). This article will not observe professional forms of dance education (specialized ballet schools) but rather investigate the formal dance education inclusion with an emphasis on elementary schools. The challenges that dance as a teaching content with its diverse forms (different styles and dance techniques) is faced with are particularly complex. It is not only shaping, colonizing the body in a certain formative protocol (related to the performing technique – classical ballet, modern dance: Graham, Limon, Cunningham, Forsythe technique, new dance styles: hip-hop, jazz dance, etc.), but also simultaneous development of perhaps not easily visible benefits that harmonize the development of an individual. The ability to eloquently, individually, and dedicatedly set and realize certain task is one of the premises of contemporary dance education.

In modern conditions, dance is not only an artistic expression or (what is the subject of this analysis) part of a teaching curriculum, but also increasingly accommodating its position in other spheres of life. Dancing as a therapeutic and prophylactic mechanism is not a novelty and this category has been developing since the middle of the 20th century. Its application varies from therapy for certain orthopedic disorders and diseases, through treatment of psychosomatic disorders. It is a method used in working with children with disabilities, but it is also an instrument for channeling negative emotions, stress and anxiety. The spectrum of possible applications in relation to dance therapy is a remarkable wide area and the results encourage further research and application of this field in various segments. In recent decades, more and more papers and books have been published on this topic, which relate to the use of dance as part of treatments and protocols for different types of medical conditions and diseases (Goodill, 2005; Chaiklin & Wengrower, 2009; Ogansyan, 2005). However, it must be emphasized that certain aspects of dance are also utilized for prevention and prophylaxis. Dance is an ideal instrument for shaping and proper development of the body. The modern lifestyle imposes a serious problem that is associated with the increased percentage of spinal deformities. If a dance is practiced as a preventive activity permanently and purposefully, deformities, incorrect posture and displacement of the spine will be significantly reduced. In this case, it would be much better to prevent, instead of eventually going under a process of medical treatments and surgical corrections.

Dance in many preschool institutions, as well as in elementary schools is used as a practice that encourages creative expression. In addition, these activities facilitate communication and peer socialization in a grouping. Not only does it contribute to building a positive attitude

towards oneself, but it also develops a feeling of belonging to a particular group. This activity brings joy and satisfaction. Through dancing, two significant disciplines are united: physical activity and creative expression.

The focus of this research is on Macedonian elementary schools. Elementary education comprises of nine grades (starting at the age of five and a half or six). It is divided into three separate segments. "The structure of elementary education, established through the Concept for nine-year elementary education, consists of three educational periods: grades 1-3, grades 4-6 and grades 7-9. Each period is relatively unified as a whole in regard to the developmental characteristics of students and of learning. Each period is also characterized with different approaches in the evaluation and assessment of student achievements, individualised teaching, knowledge, skills and student progression" (Eurydice, online). The subject structure consists of compulsory and elective subjects. In Macedonian elementary education system, students have a limited option in terms of choosing Dance as a subject. Nevertheless, it must be noted that there is a positive change by the inclusion of this subject in the list of elective subjects at the two educational levels. The subject of Dancing (fourth and fifth grade) and the subject of Dance and Folk-Dance (eighth and ninth grade). The respective elective subjects in the first two levels of elementary education are one-semester, that is, they are studied in the first or second semester. Unfortunately, in practice, these two subjects are not always opted for on the elective list. I would like to point out one positive example of the Macedonian private school NOVA International School Skopje. Within this educational institution there is an elementary and secondary school. In the curricula, the Dance subject is represented as mandatory throughout the entire elementary education and during the first two years of secondary education. In the last two years of secondary education, Dance subject is not excluded but is placed on the list of elective subjects. The scope of curriculum in elementary school NOVA varies in relation to the educational level i.e. grade, with 2 to 3 classes per week, which suggests a seriously well-developed program adapted to the needs of age, but also to the development of the personality.

Dance education is widely applied in schools in Western Europe and especially the USA. The models and forms of dance teaching cannot be unified and stereotyped, on the contrary they are variable and conditioned by the purpose and the expected results. It is important to draw attention to specific facets of dance education, organizing them into distinct categories that can be applied and incorporated into the teaching process in both elementary and secondary educational institutions. At the same time, the intention is to make projections and give certain recommendations for a future developmental direction. Specific and significant aspects i.e. benefit of dance education, will be briefly presented. Since it is not possible to fully cover all the advantages of dance education in one article, this text aims to underscore the following ones:

- Developing and Improving Memory Processes
- Developing Motor Skills and Body Coordination
- Creative Development
- Channelling, Dealing with Negative Emotions and Aggressive Behaviour

Developing and Improving Memory Processes

Dance and dancing advance memory processes. Russian dance pedagogue Nikolay Tarasov, who has been working with dancers for more than 50 years, emphasizes that dancing develops and trains three kinds of specific memory processes, namely the perceptual – the visual, the auditory or musical and the kinaesthetic or motoric. “Well-developed memory is pivotal for a dancer (...) Memory of a dancer is divided to auditory, visual and motoric” (Tarasov, 1971, p. 58). An almost identical view regarding memorization and activation of different types is given by Ling Xiaojie (2023). In this study the author writes about several types of memory:

(1) Action sequence memory. Action sequence is the basic building block in dance, including specific steps, turns, jumps and combinations. Dancers must remember and execute these sequences accurately in their performances (...)

(2) Posture memory. Posture memory involves the dancer's body position, movement, posture and coordination. These elements are crucial to the accuracy and beauty of dance. Posture memory requires dancers to have good body perception and coordination in order to maintain correct posture in performance.

(3) Emotional expression memory. The memory of emotional expression involves the dancer's understanding and internalization of the emotional requirements of dance to show them in the performance.

(4) Music memory. Music memory is the key to dance performance, and dancers must keep pace with the music rhythm. This requires them to remember the beat, speed and rhythm changes of music.

(5) Integrate different types of memories. Integrating different types of memories requires a high degree of coordination, practice and concentration to ensure that dancers consider multiple aspects at the same time in their performance (Xiaojie, 2023, p. 312).

By performing certain movements or a dance combination, students even the youngest have to activate certain parts of their body muscles in accordance with the defined rhythmic pattern and particular proxemics (spatial) organization. They are combined and initiate the application of a different pre-taught/ memorized material that is supplemented and becomes more complex in the learning process. Dancing naturally develops all three types of memory without any additional effort. Each type is significant in the learning course of the formal education. “Synaptic plasticity allows the connections between neurons in the brain to change during learning and practice. This is very important for the acquisition of dance skills, because dancers need to constantly improve and adjust their movements to achieve higher accuracy and coordination...Practice and training also help to strengthen memory” (Xiaojie, 2023, p. 318). When studying dance there are three learning methods, each individually connected in respective with the types of memorization present at a different educational level. Their application in accordance with the age level initiates improved productivity and results (Zdravkovska Djeparovska, 2011).

Regarding the connection between memorization and dancing, the research of a group of authors is interesting. Motivated by the restrictions caused by Covid pandemic, they conducted a study on the learning capacities of children who study remotely. The analyzed group included children aged 7 to 8, whereas the interviews were conducted with their parents who recorded their results before and after the instructions given by the researchers (Syarah et al., 2021). This analysis refers to measuring the effect of dancing and listening to music and their impact on the improvement of three categories that are the subject of the research, which are memory, inhibition, and mental flexibility of children at home. Parents pointed out that when monitoring the effects of activities at home, the results show a visible improvement in all three components. I will end this section with another quote from this study. "Brain training with dancing and familiar music improves children's cognitive abilities" (Syarah et al., 2021, p. 136). Dance as a complex performing medium is correlated with complex memory processes, which has an extremely positive influence on the overall mental and physical development at the initial level of education, that eventually strengthens well-being at the adolescents, and it also contributes to health benefit in relation to the elderly population group. Several authors emphasize the positive effect of dance on the development of memory and cognitive abilities of participants during dance activities (Karpati et al., 2015; Theohchariday et al., 2018; Poikonen et al., 2018).

Developing Motor Skills and Body Coordination

Dance itself implies a complex way of coordinating body movements developing motor skills in children naturally and effortlessly, which is equally visible in all age groups. "Dance integrates the coordination of intentional body movements. Synchronization with rhythmical stimuli permits the activation of both the conscious and the unconscious processes of the brain" (Ali & Siddiqui, 2016, p. 31). This is proven by several studies. One of them, which was conducted on a preschool population (around the age of four) using "street dance" practice, shows an improved general condition in all aspects: memory, coordination, mobility. The authors emphasized: "In short, after controlling for the pretest factors, we found that street-dance training does promote the development of children's EF (executive function- author note)" (Shen et al., 2020, p. 11). Another analysis (Kirsch et al., 2018), although not specifically aimed at elementary school children, presents indicative results and confirmed that dance actions develop perceptual abilities and performance in relation to the set motor and visual tasks. "Our ability to learn by physical practice as well as by observation is a key ingredient for acquiring new motor skills and is thus essential for us to survive and thrive within a social world" (Kirsch et al., 2018, p. 1).

Dancing simultaneously activates a large number of muscles, which acquires conscious, sensible and controlled movement of the body and limbs. Dance represents movements of individual parts of the body coordinated within given spatial coordinates in accordance with musical accompaniment. This in itself strengthens and improves general coordination, orientation and motor skills. This complex combination, i.e. the involvement, activation of certain muscle groups, i.e. parts of the body and their controlled movement is adopted gradually, through dance plays adapted to the age and affinities of specific groups. This contributes to improving the general coordination of movements in children. I will refer to the aforementioned

ned study, the authors note: "Second, in terms of the promotion of psychological function, hip-hop can exercise individual perception, body balance, hand-eye coordination, attention, and emotional stability, and then, promote the development of sensory integration" (Shen et al., 2020, p. 9). The ability to consciously control all parts of the body conditions the improvement of activities related to fine motor skills used in writing and drawing at younger children (from preschool and early elementary school), i.e. obtaining precision and accuracy in relation to older groups of students. A study was published in the journal *Music & Science* that empirically measured the coordination of elementary movements (tapping, walking and marching) and music (clapping hands) in children (at an average age of 5.5 years). "Rhythm coordination integrates both sensor and motor abilities needed for beat detection, timing, and motor coordination of different rhythms (e.g., in dancing, ball games)" (Tuominen et al., 2020, p. 1). This influences the children's ability to perceive given dances, but also another type of task, consciously combining different information (visual, auditory, tactile, etc.) which leads to improvement in the overall learning progress process.

Figure 1. MBUC, Dance school Skopje, author`s personal collection

As already mentioned, all this happens through creative tasks, play and within a positive atmosphere of those who are involved in the activities. Participants in dance activities achieve visible improvement through movements.

Creative Development

Generally, art including dancing, likewise contributes to stimulation and development of the creative component in students. In addition, dance encourages proper emotional development and develops individual potential in children. "One of the characteristics of art is the mobilization of the imagination. Art acts with this human trait, composing with the elements that create different meanings (...) The body in the process of creation mobilizes personal attitudes, habits and values; evokes perceptions, thoughts, lessons; evidence cultural and environmental influences; and rearranges new meanings, new conceptual schemes" (Pilla & Zancan, 2024, p. 11). Dance movement is a channel through which school population, adolescents and adults express themselves, by dancing they gain self-confidence and at the same time build positive feelings. In the case of group performances, certain rules are

established, which require the attentiveness of the participants, harmonization of attitudes and discipline. Socialization happens quite naturally and easily. However, this activity does not impose rigid acceptance of standardized protocols. Nonetheless, it motivates an individual way of expression and that individuality is esteemed and evolved. This form of self-expression through rhythmical movement and dancing has been analyzed by several researchers. "Dancing with music supports mental development and thinking development, which reflects that dancing is a tool for children to know, think, translate, interpret, and create thoughts" (Syarah et al., 2021, p. 143).

Figure 2. Dance studio Aurora, Skopje. Daria Djeparoska personal collection

Creative rhythm-dance method is used in the educational process in several countries, more precisely in more educational programs starting from preschool to adolescence. Dancing, that is, creating one's own expression, manner, and aesthetics, stimulates a sense of satisfaction and happiness. "The results of the present study highlight several areas in which individuals may benefit from world dance such as acceptance of self and others, achievement, creativity, career, culture, expression, happiness, healing, health, social support and stress relief" (Ali et al., 2016, p. 15). In this analysis, it will be presented experiences with which I have firsthand familiarity. While these experiences have not been featured in any published articles, I am well-acquainted with the results they yielded. Srna Klotz is a founder of Ô'tänamos INC., a non-profit dance organization based in New York City. The main aim of this organization is dedicated to exploring the transformative power of dance and movement. Through different programs, she had worked with diverse groups, including children from underprivileged neighborhoods, veterans with PTSD, seniors, and individuals with both Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. By implementing her own projects and practical work Srna Klotz has come to certain conclusions herself. An interview with her was prepared and conducted for this article, where she shares her experience: "Emotionally, dance provides an outlet for self-expression and helps build resilience, while socially, it fosters collaboration and trust, especially partnered or group dances. For children between the ages of 6 and 14, these benefits are especially impactful, with the added advantage that movement and music can also enhance their academic performance" (S. Klotz, personal communication, December 10, 2024).

Channelling, Dealing with Negative Emotions and Aggressive Behaviour

Referring to the structure of elementary education established through the Concept for Nine-Year Elementary education, a national document prepared by the Bureau for the Development of Education of Macedonia, I will highlight one segment from the 2015 version. In addition to other aspects, the principle of physical safety and health is presented, where the last point states: "An opportunity for all students during their regular classes to acquire skills and knowledge on how to care for and improve their health, how to deal with stress and how to resolve conflict situations with non-violent methods" (bro.gov.mk, online). Nowadays, it is of particular importance not only to discuss, but also to act in preventing the increasingly frequent conflicts among this age population. The methods for channelling and articulating aggression are different, but one of the possible quite productive method is the usage of dance i.e. movement techniques.

Impatience, anxiety, and quick often violent ways of overcoming issues among children are occurring more frequently. Aggression is created as a result of non-acceptance and lack of communication. The inability to find an adequate place in a group, rejection and impaired communication often result in bullying and violent actions. We are witnesses to the increasing incidents of peer violence, which in certain situations result in fatal reaction outcomes, unfortunately with murders (these events no longer come as information from some faraway country but have rather become our reality). How to prevent this? The study about using dance as a beneficial activity within distance learning process was mentioned above. When including dance in daily activities, parents noticed better focus and concentration, less anxiety and impatience in their children. There are numerous research studies on the topic of coping with stress and stressful situations through dance (Bräuninger, 2012; Nutu & Munteanu, 2017; Hanna, 2017; Neha, Dumaresq, & Tamplin, 2024; Christopher, Dumaresq, & Tamplin, 2024). One of these studies states "Because dance is physical, cognitive, and emotional, it is a vehicle for a person to cope with stress and become motivated and invigorated to achieve goals for wellbeing (...). However, dance is a medium through which to discharge the energy and, most significantly, to portray and scrutinize stressors in order to diminish their threat" (Hanna, 2017, p. 109).

In the USA, but also in countries of the American continent the effect of dancing is analyzed very seriously, and Dance subject is found in various school program. Besides other advantages, dancing as a mechanism enables participants to channel and get rid of accumulated negative energy and aggressiveness. It simultaneously encourages building of a collective spirit and ways of creating new types of communication (we are aware of the fact that during conflicts, most frequently there is a lack of appropriate communication, or it is completely absent). The authors Kotaman, İnceoğlu and Kotaman (2024) monitored the change in aggressive, but also oppositely introverted/shyness behavior in children. The research included a test group that attended dance classes and a control group that did not have these activities. The evaluated results refer to the pretest and post-test period during which the values were compared. The authors' conclusion is quite arithmetically precisely expressed, which is sublimated in their conclusion. "Findings revealed that contrary to control group dancing group had significant gains for pro-social behaviors and significant decrease in

aggression and shyness. Concurrently, teachers in dancing group reported that their children's aggressive behaviours showed significant decrease after the dancing program whereas no such evidence was present for control group" (Kotaman et al. 2024, p. 19 176). Another study refers to 54 elementary schools with a mixed ethnic student composition. The implemented test program for dance/movement for a period of three months outcomes positive results and a rate of reduced aggression. The authors Koshland, Wilson and Wittaker noted „Statistical results showed that teachers noticed a significant decrease of these behaviors in their students instigating fights, failing to calm down, frustration intolerance, and throwing articles“ (Koshland, et al., 2004, p. 69).

Furthermore, dance practice pretty successfully overcomes cultural differences that may easily create intolerance, tensions and the possible violent responses. Conflicts on a racial and ethnic basis are unfortunately rising. Certain school programs use dance content as a bridge for integration, but also for getting to know the "other". Cone and Purcell Cone (2016) reviewed the implementation of dance as a subject in school programs. They realized "In other programs cultural dances are emphasized to address the cultural diversity represented in the school or community as students may be learning salsa, merengue, bachata, tinikling, the hula, mayim, troika, or American square dance (...) The performances feature ballet, modern, jazz, social and cultural dance forms as a way to showcase the many ways in which students engage in dance as a means of expression and communication. Both curricular areas share a common goal, which is to teach students different ways to move and collaborate, and to see dance as a means of self-fulfilment and expression (Cone & Purcell Cone, 2016, p. 4). If we know that the acceptance and recognition of diversity is most easily applied through cultural programs, the arts, and implicitly the dance, the question arises why wouldn't we utilize that?

Figure 3. S.H.E Inspire, Pleasantville, New Jersey, Srna Klotz personal collection

Srna Klotz took part in the project of S.H.E Inspirea nonprofit organization founded to empower and inspire African American girls to rise above societal stereotypes. This organization was located at a community center in Pleasantville, NJ, a community faced high crime rates, with nearly 25% of the population living below the poverty line. Based on her experience with this project, she highlighted its importance:

I recognized the transformative power of the arts. Through dance students not only get outlet for emotional expression and creativity but also a space for them to build resilience, confidence, and a sense of community—tools that extend far beyond the studio (...) Through shared experiences of movement and rhythm, students develop collaboration, mutual understanding, and empathy, forming bonds that can lead to lifelong friendships. This sense of belonging is crucial for emotional development, as it creates a supportive environment where students can grow both individually and as part of a community. On the Dancefloor, we are all the same. We are learning together. We're laughing together. Now, when children are more disconnected with each other than ever having an activity like dancing and fostering sense of belonging, can serve as a powerful tool in preventing violence and promoting peaceful conflict resolution among students, reducing the likelihood of harmful behavior such as mass violence (S. Klotz, personal communication, December 10, 2024).

Dance is a platform for future collaborations and better mutual understanding of various heterogeneous group.

Conclusion

In this discussion, I have sought to identify four recognized and important categories of benefits. It is essential to underline that these categories are not isolated; rather, they are intertwined and complementary, creating a rich and complex effect. While it is feasible to consider them independently in a theoretical context, they naturally coalesce and enhance each other during the educational experience. This short analysis examines the advantages of integrating dance into the educational framework. What we have noted is a rather brief overview of the benefits supported by results obtained with specific research. I emphasize that these research and studies are not as extensive as in other disciplines and fields, yet they hold exceptional significance for the theoretical and scientific understanding of this domain. Dance education can be formal (within school curricula) or informal (through dance sections and extracurricular activities). According to the above, it should certainly be incorporated as part of educational curricula. In Western countries, the tendency of introducing dance is based on tradition. Experiences show that this trend of introducing dance content (across various profiles and styles) is growing.

If this tendency is applied in Macedonian education, which strives to be compatible with global educational practices, there is no doubt that the scope of dance as content, or rather a teaching subject, should be extended. It is advisable to introduce Dance as a distinct subject at all three educational levels. Notably, the presence of this discipline in all three phases is particularly significant for student development. The programs in terms of the content itself (a particular style, appropriately modelled exercises and adapted creative tasks) ought to take into consideration the age, the cultural context and intended goals. The dance programs should incorporate all these specifics. It is of essential importance not to literally copy current programs, but to tailor proper content that will be functional in the in the Macedonian education system based on acquired experiences and knowledge. Definitely, the initial step is to focus on implementing dance activities, i.e. subjects, into the teaching curriculum.

Subsequently, we should systematically upgrade and expand it to benefit the needs of the students and the cause of the subject, taking into account the Macedonian social context and educational strategies.

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UTJECAJ PLESNOG OBRAZOVANJA NA RAZVOJ UČENIKA OSNOVNE ŠKOLE

Sažetak

Plesno obrazovanje u Makedoniji slabo je zastupljeno u nastavnim planovima i programima osnovnog obrazovanja (s izuzetkom dva izborna predmeta). Naprotiv, posljednjom reformom koja je provedena kod nekih predmeta umjetničkog profila, konkretno u nastavi glazbe, tjedni fond sati je smanjen. Za razliku od ove situacije, u mnogim razvijenijim zemljama umjetnosti su segmentirane u različite obrazovne predmete, a ples je uključen u različite stupnjeve obrazovanja s višegodišnjim programima. Postavlja se pitanje je li plesna umjetnost potrebna kao samostalan predmet i kakva je korist ovakve nastave? Odgovor je naravno potvrđan, ples ima velike pozitivne učinke na razvoj mlade populacije. Prednosti su brojne. Kako bi se dobila jasna i preciznija slika, pozitivnih učinaka ovog učenja učinci su razvrstani u nekoliko skupina. U prvoj je skupini prikazan učinak razvoja memorijskih procesa kod učenika koji se postiže metodama koje se koriste u plesnom treningu. Druga skupina učinaka odnosi se na razvoj koordinacije i motorike. Sljedeći značajan učinak je razvoj kreativnosti. U suvremenom svijetu sve se češće susrećemo s agresijom i negativnim emocijama. Provedena istraživanja pokazuju da ples i u ovom segmentu ima pozitivan učinak. U izlaganju će biti navedene plesne forme koje odgovaraju različitim uzrastima te metodologija njihovog proučavanja. Izneseno će biti potkrijepljeno znanstvenim istraživanjima u ovom području koja se provode posljednjih godina i daju mjerljive rezultate.

Ključne riječi: ples, osnovno obrazovanje, efekti, metode